

THE ESSENTIAL CONTENT OF THE CONCEPT OF TAX BURDEN IN THE ECONOMY

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Annotation: *This article examines issues such as the theory of taxation and the practical implications of the tax burden. It explores determining the most favorable levels of the tax burden and calculating it.*

Key words: *Tax, tax burden, levels of tax burden, calculation of tax burden, absolute tax burden, entrepreneur*

In both theory and practice of taxation, the problem of determining the most favorable tax burden has always existed. The level of tax revenues is influenced not only by socio-economic factors but also by the effective utilization of the tax system and its ability to fulfill its tasks. The impact of these functions can be assessed by examining the tax burden on economic entities. Ranking the economy based on the overall level of the tax burden is also increasingly important.

Many economists have studied the level of the tax burden and its influence on economic development and the standard of living of the population through taxes. The use of reasonable, fair, and realistic options for the tax burden during a certain period ensures the efficient development of the economy in many developed countries. When managing the economy through taxes, particularly in achieving sectoral harmony, it is necessary to study the relevant tax burden situation in different sectors and industries.

The tax burden on economic entities reflects the state's tax policy and provides a qualitative description of any tax system. Furthermore, the level of taxes is determined by both the efficiency of social production and the financial resources required by the state. Therefore, reducing the tax burden depends primarily on reducing state expenses and the level of payment for social services.

Some experts associate the effectiveness of the tax system with the contribution of taxes to GDP, while others recommend calculating the tax burden by considering all payments, including allocations to extra-budgetary funds and the volume of product sales.

Describing the distribution of the tax burden among members of society, it can be said that most production taxes, especially indirect taxes, are included in the cost of goods and ultimately borne by the consumer. The tax burden on the population, or the tax potential per capita, can be determined in relation to the average per capita income.

Based on this, when calculating the tax potential of the entire country, the tax burden is calculated as the sum of all tax amounts and insurance contributions. When calculating the tax burden related to the labor of hired employees, all taxes are added together, and the weight of the tax burden is proposed to be determined by the share of the value weight and adjusted (increased) by the tax burden coefficient of the population.

The aforementioned methodology for calculating the tax burden as a tax share in GDP is simple and widely used in foreign countries. However, currently, this methodology does not allow for comparing the level of tax burden at the micro level for enterprises in different production branches and sectors of the economy.

The Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the State Tax Committee have recommended a methodology for calculating the tax burden on legal entities. In this methodology, the tax burden is determined by a ratio that includes all calculated taxes, fees, and other mandatory payments, the calculated amount of payments to extra-budgetary funds, the volume of product sales, and income from other sales.

An increase in wage expenses affects the increase in payments to extra-budgetary funds. Additionally, fines paid as a result of late tax payments can also contribute to an increase in the tax burden.

When determining the tax burden, it is necessary to distinguish between absolute and relative tax burden. The absolute tax burden represents the total amount of taxes, fees, and other mandatory payments transferred to budgetary and extra-budgetary funds, indicating the total tax liabilities of economic entities. In statistical reports, this indicator includes the actual transfer of tax payments to the budget and mandatory insurance contributions to extra-budgetary funds, as well as monitoring these payments.

Insurance contributions paid by business entities to extra-budgetary funds are compulsory payments with a tax character, and they should be taken into account when calculating the tax burden.

However, the absolute tax burden does not represent a conflict of tax obligations. This indicator does not reflect the compatibility of the sources of payment with the number of taxpayers. Therefore, it is more appropriate to use the relative tax burden indicator.

The relative tax burden is understood as the ratio of its absolute amount to the newly created value, which includes the contribution of taxes, fees, and other mandatory payments, as well as its dependence on the newly created value.

The source of tax payments is the value added. Value added refers to the value of goods and services, reduced by intermediate consumption, which is viewed as consumption from the perspective of further production. Different methods of tax collection aim to obtain a portion of the added value.

Thus, the impact of the tax burden on business activity is undeniable. Its effect can be either negative or positive. When the tax burden is heavy, business activity slows down and may even come to a halt. On the other hand, a relatively lighter tax burden stimulates business activity. However, it is not appropriate to interpret a reduction in the tax burden as the sole reason for the development of entrepreneurship. Additionally, reducing the tax burden has its logical limit, which is largely associated with the expenses to be covered by the state budget. Therefore, in our view, in order to further stimulate business activities in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to consider the redistribution of the tax burden among different sectors of the economy as an urgent issue, rather than further easing the tax burden.

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